

Review

Biological fertilizers and their role in plant growth

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ABSTRACT

The demand for food is increasing all over the world as a result of the massive population increase. Therefore, the countries of the world including Iraq are considered to be consumers of chemical fertilizers, in proportion to the cultivated areas. Especially, the nitrogenous fertilizers are a result of the bad effects of irrational use of these fertilizers. The world today has turned toward clean agricultural technologies or sustainable agriculture in order to reduce pollution by using natural materials instead of traditional fertilizers such as fertilizers and biological fertilizers. That works and helps to increase food production for both humans and animals, this trend is toward the use of natural materials in the composting process, and it is considered one of the clean or sustainable agriculture techniques through which production can be increased in quantity and quality.

Keywords Bio-fertilizers, Agriculture techniques, Microorganisms, Environment

1. Introduction

According to the studies conducted by researchers, current soil and crop management systems are not sustainable or able to maintain this wealth. The excessive use of chemical fertilizers resulted in a lack of compensation for the nutrients in the soil, which led to a clear decline in soil productivity. This decline in soil productivity did not happen by coincidence, but due to the excessive and improper use of chemical fertilizers for a long period. When peoples need for food increased, they began to search for new sources and technologies aiming to increase the productivity and improve the product quality on one hand, and reduce the effect on the environment on the other hand, by adopting many mechanisms that help people to reduce the chemical or traditional fertilizers which the use of it is becoming a danger on the environment [1]. On the other hand, the use of chemical fertilizers, whether they are nitrogenous or phosphates, often results in some problems, such as losing a large amount of nitrogen added through the biological reduction of nitrates or through the process of reversing nitrification and volatilization of ammonia in addition to washing a quantity of nitrogen element through ground water, ultimately causing a pollution to the environment and thus harm to human health. In addition to the excessive use of nitrogenous substances leads to an environmental problem, nitrate pollution, as it is considered an environmental pollutant, undesirable and harmful to humans, especially children and animals [2]. Therefore, the bio-fertilizers are reliable and inexpensive plant food sources instead of mineral fertilizers that have a great impact on polluting the environment, whether it is soil or water [3].

2. What are the bio-fertilizers?

It is microbial pollen of various highly active microbial genera, which may contain fungal or algal genera [4]. Bio-fertilizers result from isolation, purification and characterization of selected strains of beneficial microorganisms in the soil and their multiplication in suitable farms until use. They are either mixed with seeds before planting or contaminated with seedlings or added directly to the soil in order to provide the plant with nutrients by activating them in the soil or in a Rhizosphere layer [5]. These fertilizers are now produced in the form of commercial products that can be used at the ring level by the ordinary farmer, as their use has led to clear tangible results in terms of reducing the rate of nitrogen and phosphate fertilization as well as raising crop productivity as an indirect result of changes in soil conditions and plant physiology [6]. The use of this fertilizer for a few consecutive years can reduce the need for mineral fertilizers and that the effect may not be noticed in the first year of use or for the first time, but rather is achieved in successive years of use on the same land with a very high increase in the yield and its quality by increasing the readiness of nutrients in the soil [7]. Bio-fertilizers include many microorganisms that differ according to the purpose used for this fertilizer and can be divided in terms of their nature and behavior in the soil into:

1. Symbiotic bio-fertilizers: they are produced from microorganisms that live a symbiotic life with the roots of plants. These microbes supply plants with some nutrients while taking their nutritional needs, especially the source of carbon from the plant, meaning that there is an exchange of benefit between two different organisms that live with each other, and they provide each other with the benefit, including the rhizobia for legumes, which began to be marketed on commercial carrier in many countries long years ago [8].
2. Non- symbiotic bio-fertilizers: This type of fertilizer is produced from microorganisms that live freely in the soil, meaning they obtain their needs from the soil. Among these organisms are (*Azospirillum*, *Azotobacter* and non-symbiotic nitrogen fixers) include phosphate solvents such as *Mycorrhizia* and *Bacillus* sp. They are highly efficient in dissolving insoluble phosphates in the soil [9]. They also include a group of blue-green algae that are used as pollen in rice-grown soils. The secretions of some root plants encourage the vital activity of these organisms, thus increasing their efficiency as a bio-fertilizer.

3. The characteristics of the organism used for bio-fertilization

The selected strain is characterized by the ability to compete throughout its stay in the soil, to resist predators and parasites in the soil, to be unaffected by the chemicals added to the seeds in order to protect them, and it must be characterized by the stability of the genotype of the strains, i.e. it is resistant to environmental conditions such as drought and heat, and the most important advantage is the ability to achieve the goal of using it at the right time [8, 10].

4. The importance of bio-fertilizers

Bio-fertilizers work to reduce environmental pollution by rationalizing the consumption of chemical fertilizers which are harmful to the environment:[11, 12], as it was found that treating the *Sesamum indicum* L. , *Pseudomonas* bacteria with half the dose of chemical fertilizers gave a growth equal to the treatment with a full dose of bio-fertilization, The treatment (half dose of chemical fertilization with bio-fertilization) also increased the yield with oil by 33.3%, while the yield protein increased by 47.5% compared to the single full dose of chemical fertilization treatment[13]. They also increase the readiness of nutrients and facilitate their absorption. The microorganisms secrete stimulants for growth (Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) [14], they improve the physical, chemical and biological properties, as they increase soil fertility by increasing the numbers of microorganisms in soil, and thus a positive impact on plants[15]. As the author [16], explained that the addition of bio-fertilizer in all its forms led to an increase in the growth indicators

of *Zea mays* L., as well as Plant Growth Promoting Fungi (PGPF), used as a bio-fertilizer, produces some fungal antibiotics that work on Plant disease resistance by acting as a bio-control [17], thus reducing the use of pesticides which are also harmful to the environment, [18, 19]. They perform the process of biological fixation of nitrogen (atmospheric nitrogen) and this leads to a reduction in the use of nitrogenous mineral fertilizers, and some organisms dissolve phosphate in Calcareous soils and make them suitable for plant growth, as well as work to strengthen the growth of the root and vegetative system of plants through the production of plant hormones such as gibberellins, cytokinines and auxins [20]. They also work to improve the properties of the soil, especially sandy soils, through the production or excretion of sugar materials such as EPS, LPS [21, 22] as the researcher [23] showed that the sugar substance (EPS) also has a role in protecting plants from environmental stresses, it also plays a role in the attachment of bacteria to plant roots and thus the formation of root nodes during the symbiotic relationship which leads to the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen and its conversion into ammonia.

5. The required measurements to maintain the efficiency of bio-fertilizers:

1. Storing of bio-fertilizers in a cool place, and at room temperature as a maximum.
2. Not to mix bio-fertilizers directly with chemical fertilizers or pesticides.
3. Using the fertilizer before its expiration date.
4. Choosing the appropriate method for fertilization as well as the appropriate time, taking into account the appropriate bio-fertilizer for each crop [24].

6. The currently used bio-fertilizers

Below are examples of the currently used fertilizers:

1. Biogen is a bio-fertilizer which contains Azotobacter with nitrogen-fixing Azosperillim. This bacterium secretes root stimulants, which helps to absorb nutrients and improve the natural soil properties and thus increase vegetative growth of the plant.
2. Potasiomage is enriched with Bacillus bacteria that transforms the unabsorbed potassium into an absorbable form.
3. Fulzyme fertilizer contains Bacillus bacteria with Pseudomonas bacteria, which works to dissolve phosphorous in the soil and make it more accessible to the plant and improve plant growth by increasing the spread of roots.
4. Blogeine contains blue-green algae that are able to fix bio- nitrogen in their bodies by converting it into nitrogenous compounds that the plant can benefit from.
5. Micropen is a fertilizer which contains a wide range of microorganisms that increase soil fertility and reduce the rates of addition of nitrogen and phosphate fertilizers and other elements by no less than 25% and reduce environmental pollution problems.
6. Phosphorene is a fertilizer that contains active bacteria which convert triple phosphate and inaccessible calcium into monophosphate and accessible calcium, and it is added after planting.
7. Al-Awqadain is a biological nitrogen fertilizer for leguminous crops, which is mixed with the seeds before planting.
8. Nemalese is fertilizer and insecticides to eliminate nematodes [25].

7. Conclusion

According to the studies conducted on the use of bio-fertilizers for crops, bio-fertilizers lead to an increase in the final yield, in quantity and quality, by 10-20 % of cereal crops, and also provide a large part of the important nutrients for the plant (25% air nitrogen + 50% dissolved phosphate) and that their prices are very low as compared with the prices of chemical fertilizers, as they reduce production costs due to the low price and production costs.

Conflict of Interest

The author reports no conflict of interest.

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